

YOSHLAR TARBIYASIDA-MA'NAVİYATNING O'RNI

Yo'ldasheva Marjona

Osiyo Xalqaro Universiteti Pedagogika
yo'nalishi 1-bosqich talabasi.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10825809>

Annotatsiya. Bugungi kunda yoshlar hayotida-ma'naviy tarbiya eng dolzarb masala hisoblanadi. Ma'naviy tarbiya bu-bizning kimligimizni, hayotimiz mazmunini, hayotning oq qorasini ifodalovchi tushuncha hisoblanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Ma'naviyat, Birinchi Prezident, Islom Karimov, Shavkat Mirziyoyev.

THE ROLE OF SPIRITUALITY IN YOUTH EDUCATION

Abstract. Today, spiritual education is considered the most urgent issue in the life of young people. Spiritual education is a concept that expresses who we are, the meaning of our life, the black and white of life.

Key words: Spirituality, First President, Islam Karimov, Shavkat Mirziyoyev.

РОЛЬ ДУХОВНОСТИ В ВОСПИТАНИИ МОЛОДЕЖИ

Аннотация. Сегодня духовное воспитание считается самым актуальным вопросом в жизни молодежи. Духовное образование — это концепция, которая выражает то, кем мы являемся, смысл нашей жизни, черное и белое жизни.

Ключевые слова: Духовность, Первый Президент, Ислам Каримов, Шавкат Мирзиёев.

Tarbiya - har qanday jamiyat, har qanday mamlakat hayotida hal qiluvchi ahamiyat kasb etadi. Yosh avlodning umuman jamiyat a'zolarining tarbiyasi bilan yetarlicha shug'ullanmagan mamlakat inqirozga yuz tutadi. Tarbiya bizning hayotimizda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Insonning o'sishi, rivojlanishi jarayonida - ma'naviy tarbiyaning o'rni beqiyos.

Ma'naviyat nima?

Ma'naviyat - arab. manolar majmui. Insonning ruhiy va aqliy olamini ifodalovchi tushuncha. U kishilarning huquqiy, falsafiy, badiiy, axloqiy, diniy tasavvurlarini o'z ichiga oladi.

Jamiyatda yoshlar tarbiyasi muhim ahamiyatga ega, shu bilan birga ularning ma'naviy tarbiyasi ham yuksak ahamiyatga ega. Birinchi Prezidentimiz Islom Abdug'aniyevich Karimov o'zining „Yuksak ma'naviyat-yengilmas kuch“ asarida „Ma'naviyat insonni ruhan poklanish, qalban ulg'ayishiga chorlaydigan, odamning ichki dunyosini, irodasini, baqquvat o'iymon - e'tiqodini butun qiladigan, vijdonini uyg'otadigan, beqiyos kuch, uning barcha kurashlar mezonidir“ deya ta'rif beradilar.

Darhaqiqat ma'naviyat insonning qon-qoni, suyak-suyagiga, yillar davomida ona suti, oila tarbiyasi, ajdodlar o'giti, Vatan tuyg'usi, bu hayotning ba'zida achchiq ba'zida quvonchli saboqlari bilan qatra-qatra singib boradi.

Ma'naviyat bu - insonning, xalqning, jamiyatning va davlatning buyuk boyligi va kuch qudratidir. Bu hayotda ma'naviy tarbiyasi yo'q insonning manqurtdan farqi bo'lmaydi. U faqatgina ipli qo'g'irchoq kabi insonlar tomonidan boshqariladi. Aynan shu sababdan sho'rolar hukumronligida avvalambor insonning ma'naviy tarbiyasi, uning qadr-qimmatini yo'q qilingan.

Chunki bizning jamiyatda kim bo'lishimizni aynan ma'naviy tarbiyamiz belgilab beradi.

Ma'naviy tarbiya orqaligini biz odamiylik tuyg'ularimizni, mehr-oqibatimizni, inson ekanligimizni isbotlaymiz.

➤ Bugungi kundagi jadallik bilan ketayotgan glaballashuv jarayonida „Gumanitar muammolar“ - ommaviy qirg'in qurollari, insonga xos bo'lmagan axloqsizliklar, qurolli to'qnashuvlar, odam savdosi, diniy ekstrimizm va terrorism, oziq ovqat inqirozi, urushlar bularning kelib chiqishining bosh sababi bu - insonlarda insoniylikning sustlashishi ya'ni ma'naviy tarbiyaning yo'qolib borayotganligi bilan bog'liqdir.

➤ Bugungi kunda milliy o'zlik va ma'naviy tarbiya insonlar oldidagi eng dolzarb masalalardan biridesak adashmaymiz. Chunki ma'naviy tarbiyasi bo'lmagan - milliy o'zligini anglamaydi. Milliy o'zligini anglamagan insondan esa - eng vahshiy mavjudod chiqadi. Chunki uning o'zligi yo'q, milliy o'zlik bo'lmagandan keyin hayotda qadrlaydigan narsasi bo'lmaydi, hayotdan aniq maqsadi yo'q. Maqsadsiz kimsadan bo'lsa -vahshiytoq mavjudod topilmaydi.

Insonlarda ma'naviy tarbiya past bo'lsa ularda o'ylash, fikrlash past bo'ladi. Bundan esa „ommaviy madaniyat“ ga taqlid qiluvchi yoshlar ko'payadi. Va bunday yoshlari bo'lgan jamiyatda rivojlanish bo'lmaydi. Unday mamlakat qulaydi. Bunday tarbiyalanayotgan yoshlar esa insoniyat fojeasi uchun xizmat qiladi.

„ Agar jamiyat hayotining tanasi iqtisodiyot bo'lsa, uning joni va ruhi ma'naviyatdir. Biz yangi O'zbekistonni barpo etishga qaror qilgan ekanmiz, ikkita mustahkam ustunga tayanamiz:

1. Bozor tamoyillariga asoslangan kuchli iqtisodiyot.
2. Ajdodlarimizning boy merosi va milliy qadriyatlarga asoslangan kuchli ma'naviyatdir. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev deya takidladi.

Xulosa o'rnida shuni ta'kidlar ekanmiz biz insonlar avvalambor o'zimizda, jamiyatda, kelajak yaratuvchisi - yoshlarimizda ma'naviy tarbiyani shakllantirishimiz uchun o'zligimizni, tariximizni, milliy va ma'naviy qadriyatlarimizni, madaniy boylıklarimizni bilishimiz darkor.

Ma'naviyatga, ma'naviy tarbiyaga inson shunchaki erisha olmaydi. Inson o'zida ma'naviy ma'naviy tarbiyani rivojlantirish uchun o'qish, o'rganish, yillar davomida izlanish orqaligina yuksak ma'naviy tarbiyaga erushadi. Ma'naviy tarbiyasi yuqori bo'lgan inson hech qachon hech bir tahdidlarga aldanmaydi. U o'z hayotida yashashdan maqsadini anglyadi.

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